

VO₂/Si-Al gel Nanocomposite Thermochromic Smart Foils: Largely Enhanced Luminous Transmittance and Solar Modulation

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Abstract

VO₂ nanoparticles with a dimension of approximately 20 nm were obtained by simple mechanical bead-milling method, which were well dispersed in the transparent silica-alumina (Si-Al) gel matrix to form nanocomposites. The VO₂/Si-Al gel thermochromic nanocomposite foils were fabricated with different VO₂ solid content and foil thickness. With 10% VO₂ loading and 3 μm foil thickness, high luminous transmittance ($T_{lum(20^{\circ}C)} = 63.7\%$ and $T_{lum(90^{\circ}C)} = 54.4\%$), and large solar modulation ability ($\Delta T_{sol} = 12\%$) can be obtained which surpasses the best reported results (nanoporous films : $T_{lum(20^{\circ}C)} = 43.3\%$, $T_{lum(90^{\circ}C)} = 39.9\%$ and $\Delta T_{sol} = 14.1\%$). This current approach provided simple and scalable synthesis method with the best combined thermochromic performance.

Keywords:

Vanadium dioxide; nanoparticle; nanocomposite; nanothermochromic; mechanical bead milling; smart window

1. Introduction

Vanadium dioxide (VO_2) has been a leading thermochromic material as it exhibits an excellent temperature-responsive behavior at a critical transition temperature (τ_c) of 341 K (68 °C) near room temperature, which makes it an excellent candidate as smart architectural glazing [1]. VO_2 transits from an infrared-transparent semiconductor state at low temperature to an infrared-reflective metallic state at high temperature; nevertheless, it retains visible transmittance [2-4]. However, the low solar energy modulation ability (ΔT_{sol}) and luminous transmittance (T_{lum}) hinder its commercialization applications [5-10].

To tackle this issue, Li et al. proposed nanothermochromism, which is defined as integrating VO_2 -based nanoparticles into transparent matrix [11]. Based on the computational data, it was claimed that VO_2 nanoparticles dispersed in a dielectric host are more advantageous than VO_2 continuous thin solid films in smart window applications as they offer much higher T_{lum} and enhanced ΔT_{sol} . The crystalline VO_2 nanoparticles produced by hydrothermal and sol-gel methods are used as functional nanofillers in various matrices (e.g.: polyurethane (PU) and polysiloxane) to form nanocomposite foils on various substrates (e.g.: float glass and polyethylene terephthalate (PET)) [12-15]. The T_{lum} and ΔT_{sol} based on nanothermochromism are summarized in **Table 1**, and are compared with the best performing nanoporous films [16]. None of the current coatings or nanocomposites could satisfy the requirement for a practical architectural window ($T_{\text{lum}} > 60\%$) while still maintaining a large solar modulation ability ($\Delta T_{\text{sol}} > 10\%$) [17, 18].

Table 1 Summary of recent studies on VO_2 nanothermochromic composites

Matrix	Nanofiller		Substrate	$T_{\text{lum}}(20^\circ\text{C})$	$T_{\text{lum}}(90^\circ\text{C})$	ΔT_{sol}
	Particles	Synthesis Method				
Polysiloxane	Tungsten-doped VO_2	Sol-gel	Float Glass	~ 60.0% at 550 nm		~ 23.2% at 2.5 μm [12]
PU	$\text{VO}_2@ \text{SiO}_2$ Core-shell	Hydrothermal	PET	~ 55.3% ~ 29.2%	~ 54.2% ~ 26.3%	~ 7.5% ~ 13.6% [15]
Sb: SnO_2 (ATO)/PU	VO_2	Hydrothermal	PET	~ 53.0%	~ 49.8%	~ 11.7% [13]
PU	Fluorine-doped VO_2	Hydrothermal	PET	~ 48.7%	~ 45.9%	~ 10.7% [14]
Ref: Nanoporous thermochromic VO_2 film *			Fused silica	~ 43.3%	~ 39.9%	~ 14.1% [16]

* The best reported results on thermochromic smart window films.

Hereby, we introduce a facile and scalable approach to prepare thermochromic foils with mechanically attrited VO₂ nanoparticles dispersed in a transparent silica-alumina (Si-Al) gel. With the optimization of VO₂ solid content and foil thickness, the foils with high visible transparency and large solar modulation ability can be obtained. This result offers ~15% enhancement of $T_{lum (average)}$ (59.1% vs. 51.4%) and comparable ΔT_{sol} (12.0% vs. 11.7%) as compared with the best reported nanothermochromic foils [13] as highlighted in **Table 1**.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Preparation of VO₂ nanoparticles

The crystalline VO₂ nanoparticles were prepared by simple bead-milling method. The micro-sized commercial VO₂ powder 23 wt% (originally 99%, Alfa Aesar) was dispersed in an organic solvent, dipropylene glycol methyl ether (DPM), in the presence of a dispersing agent, Disperbyk 180 (4.5 wt%). Subsequently, the obtained dispersion was milled for 4 h in Dyno-Mill Research Lab WAB with the use of zirconia beads at the speed of 4200 rpm, followed by settling in the ambient condition for 2 days. The nano-sized particles with nano-size were suspended in the colloidal solution, which were used for the following experiments.

2.2 Preparation of VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposites on float glass

The nano-sized dispersed VO₂ particles were mixed in a Si-Al gel with a series of solid content, 2.5%, 5%, 10%, 12.5% and 15%. The preparation method of Si-Al gel was reported by us previously [19]. The VO₂ nanoparticles and Si-Al gel were mixed using the Vortex Mixer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.) for 1 h to obtain a homogeneous composite gel. Finally, this VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposite was casted onto a float glass substrate as shown in **Fig. 1**.

Fig. 1 Preparation procedure of VO₂ nanoparticles and VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposite foils on float glass substrates.

2.3 Characterization

The morphologies and phase of VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposites were determined by x-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The micrographs and energy spectroscopic images (ESI) were collected using a Carl Zeiss LIBRA[®]120 in-column energy filter TEM equipped with an integrated OMEGA filter. XRD was performed using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer (Cu K α , λ = 0.15406 nm) with 40 kV voltage and 30 mA current. The particle size and distribution of the VO₂ nanoparticles in DPM dispersion were measured by a Nano particle-sizer analyzer (Malvern Instruments Co., Ltd., U.K.). The optical transmittance in the range of 250-2500 nm was measured with a UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer (Cary 5000, Agilent Ltd) equipped with a Linkam PE120 system peltier simple heating & cooling stage.

The integral luminous transmittance (T_{lum} , 380-780 nm) and solar transmittance (T_{sol} , 280-2500 nm) were calculated based on the recorded spectra using the following expression:

$$T_{lum/sol} = \int \varphi_{lum/sol}(\lambda) T(\lambda) d\lambda / \int \varphi_{lum/sol}(\lambda) d\lambda$$

where $T(\lambda)$ is the recorded film transmittance, φ_{lum} is the standard luminous efficiency function for the photopic vision of human eyes [20], and φ_{sol} is the solar irradiance spectrum for air mass 1.5 (corresponding to the sun standing 37° above the horizon) [21]. ΔT_{sol} is attained from $\Delta T_{sol} = T_{sol}(20^\circ\text{C}) - T_{sol}(90^\circ\text{C})$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Preparation of crystalline VO₂ nanoparticles

As shown in **Fig. 2**, after 4 h milling and 2-day sedimentation, only the nanoparticles with an average size of 329 nm were suspended in the dispersion and they were employed in this study. The inset shows the XRD patterns for the commercially available VO₂ microparticles (before bead milling) and nano-sized VO₂ particles after bead milling for 4 h. The two XRD patterns were normalized to the respective maximum intensities. The XRD data (**Fig. 2** inset) of the commercial VO₂ microparticles show that monoclinic VO₂ (M1, JCPDF No.: 82-661) is the major phase with some minor peaks (solid squares) that are mostly contributed by V₆O₁₃ (JCPDF No.: 89-100). After milling, the VO₂ monoclinic phase was maintained in nanoparticles. Meanwhile, the broadening of the full width at half maximum (FWHM) for the main peaks of after-milled sample can be clearly observed, which could be resulted from nanoscale effects. Theoretical calculations based on the Scherrer equation were applied to the (110) reflection for both before- and after-milled

samples and the results indicate that the crystal size of VO₂ particles has been changed from greater than 100 nm to ~10.7 nm after bead milling, which suggests that the bead milling leads to a reduction in VO₂ crystal size without distorting its crystal structure and hence securing the thermochromic properties.

Fig. 2 Particle size and distribution of VO₂ nanoparticles after bead-milling 4h; The Inset XRD patterns of the commercial VO₂ microparticles (red solid line) and after-milled VO₂ nanoparticles (black dotted line).

3.2 VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposite with different solid content

Fig. 3(a) displays a TEM image of pure Si-Al gel, which has homogeneous appearance and uniform morphology. **Fig. 3(b)** and **3(c)** show the morphology and distribution of VO₂ nanoparticles in the Si-Al gel matrix at different magnifications. The milled particles are non-spherical in shape and well dispersed in the matrix with no agglomeration and the particle size is approximately 20 nm. The observed particle size is less than the particle analyzer result (**Fig. 2**) which may be due to the fact that the agglomerated particles after attrition were de-agglomerated during the Vortex mixing with Si-Al gel and the polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) in the gel may help to disperse the VO₂ nanoparticles uniformly in the gel matrix. **Fig. 3(d)** shows the TEM ESI mapping image of **Fig. 3(c)**. It can be noticed that more Si and Al were migrated onto the surface of VO₂ nanoparticles in contrast to gel phase, forming a shell-like structure which encapsulates the VO₂ nanoparticles. This aggregation of Si and Al may be due to the reason that the VO₂ nanoparticles provide the heterogeneous growth sites for Si and Al favorably depositing on particles to reduce the overall free energy.

Fig. 3 TEM micrographs of (a) pure Si-Al gel, (b) VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposite foil with 10% solid content at a low magnification (x80000), (c) at a higher magnification (x100000), (d) TEM ESI mapping image of 3(c) (green: vanadium (V); blue: silicon (Si); red: aluminum (Al))

Table 2 shows the variation in the thermochromic properties of the VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposites with different VO₂ solid content with fixed foil thickness of $\sim 3.3 \mu\text{m}$. At a low VO₂ solid content ratio of 2.5%, the composite foil indicated a high T_{lum} but negligible ΔT_{sol} . As VO₂ loading was increased to 10%, the T_{lum} was reduced with increasing ΔT_{sol} and the optimized combination of thermochromic properties ($T_{\text{lum}} \sim 60\%$ and $\Delta T_{\text{sol}} \sim 8\%$) can be achieved. This could be understood that with increasing VO₂ loading, more thermochromic nanofillers contributed to enhanced ΔT_{sol} while more

visible light was scattered and absorbed, leading to reduced T_{lum} . On the other hand, both optical transmittance and solar modulation ability were decreased, when the solid content was greater than 10%. This was due to the fact that when the loading of VO₂ nanoparticles exceeded 10%, the dispersion was no longer transparent and uniform. As shown in **Fig. 4**, the composite prepared in a low (~ 5%) solid content produces a clear and flawless morphology, while the high (~ 15%) solid content sample presented many large particles agglomerates.

Table 2 The thermochromic properties of VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposite foils with different solid content ratios of VO₂ nanoparticles

Solid content of VO ₂ (wt%)	T_{lum} (%)		T_{sol} (%)		ΔT_{sol} (%)
	20 °C	90 °C	20 °C	90 °C	
2.5	80.3	81.9	76.7	76.7	-0.01
5.0	69.8	69.2	67.1	61.6	5.5
10.0	59.5	57.1	59.2	51.3	7.9
12.5	55.6	53.4	56.9	50.1	6.8
15.0	56.0	56.3	57.1	55.5	1.6

Fig. 4 Photographs of samples with different solid content of VO₂ nanoparticles at 5% and 15%.

3.3 VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposites with different foil thickness

The UV-Vis-NIR spectra of VO₂/Si-Al gel nanocomposites with different foil thickness (1, 1.4, 2, 3 μm) with fixed VO₂ solid content of 10% are shown in **Fig. 5(a)** and the calculated T_{lum} and ΔT_{sol} are shown in **Table 3**. It can be seen that with increasing thickness, the transmission difference at 2500 nm (ΔT_{sol} @ 2.5 μm) was amplified from 1.67%, 6.24%, 6.35% to 13.83% and ΔT_{sol} was boosted from 0.45% to 12.0% (as shown in **Fig. 5b**),

accompanied by enhanced solar heat shielding ability ($1-T_{\text{sol}(90^\circ\text{C})}$) [13], which efficiently assists to minimize the solar heat as well as the energy demanded for cooling in buildings during the hot summer[11, 22].

The photographs of foils with 1 μm and 3 μm thickness are shown in **Fig. 5c** and both foils are flawless and transparent. 3 μm thickness foil provides dark brown color as contrasted to light greenish color in 1 μm foil due to less solid content.

Fig. 5 (a) Transmittance spectra of foils with different thickness, (b) $1 - T_{\text{sol}(90^\circ\text{C})}$ and ΔT_{sol} change with the thickness of $\text{VO}_2/\text{Si-Al}$ gel nanocomposites (Note: higher $1 - T_{\text{sol}(90^\circ\text{C})}$ indicating better solar heat shielding ability in summer time), (c) Photographs of samples with different thickness of foils at 1.03 μm and 3.02 μm

It is worth noting that the sample with foil thickness of 3 μm provides large ΔT_{sol} ($\sim 12.0\%$) with combined high integrated averaged T_{lum} ($\sim 60\%$). This result surpasses the best performing nanothermochromic foils [13] as highlighted in Table 1. Compared with nanoporous films [16], with slightly reduced ΔT_{sol} (12% v.s. 14.1%), dramatically enhanced averaged T_{lum} (59% v.s. 41.6%) can be achieved. This may due to the uniform dispersion of the nanoparticles in the gel matrix and much decreased particle size ($\sim 20\text{nm}$) which is well below the wavelength of visible light (refer to **Fig. 3**).

Table 3 The thermochromic properties of VO₂/Si-Al nanocomposite foil with different foil thicknesses

Thickness (μm)	T_{lum} (%)		T_{sol} (%)		ΔT_{sol} (%)
	20°C	90°C	20°C	90°C	
1.0	78.7	79.4	74.9	74.4	0.5
1.4	71.1	71.2	68.1	65.2	2.9
2.0	72.0	69.4	68.8	63.4	5.4
3.0	63.7	54.4	61.9	49.9	12.0

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, VO₂ nanoparticles with a dimension of approximately 20 nm were successfully obtained by simple mechanical bead-milling method and VO₂/Si-Al nanocomposite foil was formed by mixing the attrited VO₂ with Si-Al gel. This simple and scalable approach produced samples with significantly enhanced T_{lum} (~ 60%), large ΔT_{sol} (~ 12%). This combination of both enhanced T_{lum} and ΔT_{sol} exceeds the best reported nanothermochromic samples and nanoporous sample. It is the first result with T_{lum} (~ 60%) and ΔT_{sol} (> 10%) which satisfies the optical qualifications for the potential commercial applications in smart windows.

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References

- [1] M. Saeli, C. Piccirillo, I.P. Parkin, R. Binions, I. Ridley, Energy Build. 42 (2010) 1666.
- [2] P.V. Kamat, J. Phys. Chem. Lett. 2 (2011) 839.
- [3] J. Nag, R.F. Haglund, J. Phys.-Condens. Mater. 20 (2008) 264016.
- [4] N. Wang, Y. Huang, S. Magdassi, D. Mandler, H. Liu, Y. Long, RSC Adv. 3 (2013) 7124.
- [5] M. Zhou, J. Bao, M. Tao, R. Zhu, Y. Lin, X. Zhang, Y. Xie, Chem. Commun. 49 (2013) 6021.
- [6] N. Wang, S. Magdassi, D. Mandler, Y. Long, Thin Solid Films 534 (2013) 594.
- [7] Y.F. Gao, H.J. Luo, Z.T. Zhang, L.T. Kang, Z. Chen, J. Du, M. Kanehira, C.X. Cao, Nano Energy 1 (2012) 221.
- [8] Z.T. Zhang, Y.F. Gao, Z. Chen, J. Du, C.X. Cao, L.T. Kang, H.J. Luo, Langmuir 26 (2010) 10738.
- [9] S.Y. Li, G.A. Niklasson, C.G. Granqvist, J. Appl. Phys. 109 (2011) 113515.

- [10] N.R. Mlyuka, G.A. Niklasson, C.G. Granqvist, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 95 (2009) 171909.
- [11] S.Y. Li, G.A. Niklasson, C.G. Granqvist, *J. Appl. Phys.* 108 (2010) 063525.
- [12] Y.F. Lu, S.X. Zhou, G.X. Gu, L.M. Wu, *Thin Solid Films* 534 (2013) 231.
- [13] Y.F. Gao, S.B. Wang, L.T. Kang, Z. Chen, J. Du, X.L. Liu, H.J. Luo, M. Kanehira, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (2012) 8234.
- [14] L. Dai, S. Chen, J.J. Liu, Y.F. Gao, J.D. Zhou, Z. Chen, C.X. Cao, H.J. Luo, M. Kanehira, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 15 (2013) 11723.
- [15] Y.F. Gao, S.B. Wang, H.J. Luo, L. Dai, C.X. Cao, Y.L. Liu, Z. Chen, M. Kanehira, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (2012) 6104.
- [16] L.T. Kang, Y.F. Gao, H.J. Luo, Z. Chen, J. Du, Z.T. Zhang, *ACS Appl. Mater. Int.* 3 (2011) 135.
- [17] M.A. Sobhan, R.T. Kivaisi, B. Stjerna, C.G. Granqvist, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* 44 (1996) 451.
- [18] C.S. Blackman, C. Piccirillo, R. Binions, I.P. Parkin, *Thin Solid Films* 517 (2009) 4565.
- [19] C. Liu, N. Wang, Y. Long, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 283 (2013) 222.
- [20] G. Wyszecki, W.S. Stiles, *Color Science: Concepts and Methods, Quantitative Data and Formulae*, second ed., Wiley, New York, 2000.
- [21] ASTM G173-03. Standard Tables of Reference Solar Spectral Irradiance. Direct Normal and Hemispherical on a 37° Tilted Surface, Annual Book of ASTM Standards, American Society of Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, PA, 2003.
- [22] S. Elmas, S. Korkmaz, S. Pat, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 276 (2013) 641.